

D3.1 Opportunities for leverage and upscaling

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Summary

This deliverable consists of a cross-case synthesis of the social-ecological system analyses (D2.3) identifying underlying root causes of biodiversity loss, but also opportunities for leverage and amplification by disentangling both bottom-up and top-down processes that determine the status quo of the social-ecological systems by supporting or challenging local transformative innovations. Concretely, it offers a compilation and analysis of the root causes of biodiversity loss, challenges and barriers to transformative change, leverage points, and amplification processes that characterize each of the nine BIOTraCes case studies. While each case study contains highly complex and unique social-ecological constellations, this deliverable shows the communalities and difficulties that niche innovators share across places when trying to enact transformative change.

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1 Introduction: Objective and outline of D3.1

This deliverable consists of a cross-case synthesis of the social-ecological system analyses (D2.3) identifying underlying root causes of biodiversity loss, but also opportunities for leverage and amplification by disentangling both bottom-up and top-down processes that determine the status quo of the social-ecological systems by supporting or challenging local transformative innovations. Concretely, it offers a compilation and analysis of the root causes of biodiversity loss, challenges and barriers to transformative change, leverage points, and amplification processes that characterize each of the nine BIOTraCes case studies. While each case study contains highly complex and unique social-ecological constellations, this deliverable shows the communalities and difficulties that niche innovators share across places when trying to enact transformative change.

This deliverable is structured as follows: Chapter 2 embeds D3.1 in the broader BIOTraCes context, by showing the connections to previous BIOTraCes outputs and the data collection process implemented with consortium partners, through workshops and interviews conducted under WP 3 and the WP2 monitoring forms and case study reports. Chapter 3 introduces the theoretical and conceptual background, with an emphasis on the recent IPBES transformative change assessments (2025). Chapter 4 describes the methodological approach for the data analysis, while Chapter 5 presents the results through a compilation of the root causes of biodiversity loss, challenges and barriers to transformative change, current leverage points and amplification processes prevalent in the BIOTraCes cases, before turning to a discussion of cross-case findings. Finally, Chapter 6 concludes with a discussion of the complex and dynamic interplay of top-down and bottom-up processes that strongly impact the transformative potential of each of the cases.

2 How this deliverable has been created

2.1 Connection to previous BIOTraCes deliverables

This deliverable builds upon the previous outputs of BIOTraCes, and specifically on the work derived from WP2 and 3. Concretely, this document is a continuation of D2.3 “social-ecological system analyses” that contains the nine social-ecological system narratives corresponding to the BIOTraCes case studies. Each case study narrative in D2.3 provides a summary of the complex interplay of how values, types of knowledge, power dynamics, decision-making processes, ecological processes, institutional (e.g. market) dynamics and multi-level governance frameworks do shape the dynamics of social-ecological relationships, interactions, and co-dependencies. This document departs from the D2.3 Social-ecological system analyses by providing a cross-case synthesis of previous findings.

D3.1 is embedded into the overall structure of WP3, that is, for its creation a common approach has been applied across all the WP3 tasks, involving continuous meetings with WP3 tasks leaders, that led to a common approach for data collection concerning all WP3 tasks and the collective writing up of the D3.2 report regarding “strategies and approaches for just, transformative change”. This report identifies strategies and approaches that may support transformative change towards strengthened biodiversity, grounded in principles of social equity. Each chapter of D.3.2 focuses on different dimensions of change: leverage and scaling/amplification (T3.1), overall strategic pathways for biodiversity initiatives (T3.2), strategies for learning, co-creation, consultation and dialogue (T3.3), just and effective governance (T3.4), and biodiversity interdependencies of the Sustainable

Development Goals (T3.5). A more detailed description of this process can be found in the D3.2.

2.2 Collecting data from consortium partners

D3.1 builds upon secondary data collected and provided by consortium partners. Each partner developed their own approach to research design. An in-depth description of the case studies, their site-specific findings, and the methods applied can be found in the Case study reports Deliverable D2.5. For the elaboration of this deliverables, BIOTraCes consortium partners then shared interpretations of their data in both workshop and interview format, guided by questions and prompts relevant to T3.1.

Workshops:

Workshop 1: Live meeting, Portugal, May 2024. In this WP3 workshop conducted with the whole project consortium and drawing on a world café format, each WP3 task prepared several questions relevant for their task. As for T3.1, BIOTraCes researchers were invited to reflect on the following:

1. Can you identify leverage points or best practices in your case study that should be upscaled towards the broader impact sector? How could these practices be upscaled? What would be specific pathways to do so?
2. How can alternative framings of the social-ecological systems in your case studies be embedded in broader institutional context (i.e., the impact sector)?
3. Can you point to root causes of biodiversity loss in your case study that may hinder such an upscaling and embedding of plural forms of knowledge?

Workshop 2: Live meeting, Hungary, May 2025. In this WP3 workshop conducted with the whole project consortium and drawing on a world café format, each WP3 task prepared several questions relevant for their task. As for T3.1, participants were invited to reflect on the following:

1. What are the major root causes of your case study which your biodiversity innovation is aiming to overcome? including underlying causes, indirect drivers, direct drivers
2. In already identified opportunities for leverage, are they amplifying within, out, beyond?

Workshop 3: Live meeting, Hungary, May 2025. High impact sectors: In this 1hour workshop, the goal was to zoom on to BIOTraCes four high impact sectors and challenges and barriers resulting from them on the ground in the local case study context. This was a first approximation to the high impact sectors as the whole of the project. It consisted of:

1. Mapping case studies on IBPES wheels of lock-ins: In case study teams: discuss how your case study maps onto the IBPES wheel. Which lock-ins do you encounter in your case study?
2. Mapping impact sectors on IBPES wheels of lock-ins: One group per impact sector (case studies teams go to their related impact sector): discuss the lock-ins depicted in the IBPES wheel and how they relate to the impact sector your case study is embedded in.

Interviews: two rounds of interviews with consortium partners were conducted by WP3 task leaders to gather more case study specific information related to each task. More detail can be found in D3.2.

Interview round 1: online, February/March 2025. Questions specific to D3.1 :

1. Top-down initiatives in the local case study: Identify top-down (institutional) biodiversity initiatives that could be considered opportunities for leverage, e.g. by challenging the business-as-usual and those that are blocking change (as perceived by the bottom-up initiatives).
2. Bottom-up/ grassroots biodiversity innovations in the local case study: Identify biodiversity innovations and driving actors in the case study that can be considered an opportunity for leverage. Are there already processes of upscaling/ amplification (supportive factors and driving actors?)
3. Barriers/lock-ins: Which obstacles or barriers or lock-ins are present in your case study that prevent an upscaling? Which are the constraining factors and actors?

Interview round 2: online, July/September 2025. Questions specific to D3.1:

1. Which of the four prototypes in the figure below best describes your case? Why? What are the typical barriers you encounter in your case study (e.g. those mentioned in the figure, or others)?
2. Where and how would you embed (i) the high impact sector, and (ii) broader civil society in the prototype relating to your case study? What is their role in relation to your biodiversity innovation?
3. Considering your prototype, where would you identify opportunities for upscale and leverage in your case study? How is your impact sector leveraging transformative change, e.g. through positive subsidies? Are there specific innovations, policies, approaches in your case study that could be applied in the high impact sector?
4. Who are the relevant top-down actors in your case study (at which policy scales are they)?

Monitoring Forms and D2.5 Case study reports: As part of WP2, each consortium partner has been documenting and tracking the case study evolutions in periodically in project internal monitoring forms, that were used to prepare the final and published case study reports (see deliverable D2.5). Those documents were additionally consulted for the preparation of this deliverable, with a specific emphasis on the nine social-ecological system analyses prepared under D2.3.

3 Overcoming root causes through leverage points and amplification processes

Figure 1. IPBES wheel of challenges and barriers to transformative change (SPM 2025 transformative change assessment).

3.1 IPBES Root causes and challenges to transformative change

The latest IPBES transformative change assessment (2024) argues that to achieve transformative change towards a just and sustainable world, close attention must be paid to the root causes that currently drive biodiversity loss. Based on a review of the state of art, IPBES thereby distinguishes underlying causes, i.e., deeply rooted social and cultural patterns, from direct (e.g. land use change, pollution, exploitation) and indirect drivers (e.g. institutional/ governance, demographic, economic, technological factors) of biodiversity loss. Underlying causes can be understood as the root of the root of direct and indirect drivers and encompass broadly i) disconnection from and domination over nature, ii) concentration of power and wealth, iii) prioritization of short-term, individual and material gains. These three broad underlying causes are understood as directly shaping, impacting, and driving the direct and indirect drivers of biodiversity loss. Disconnection and domination of nature thereby are derived from a dominant worldview in which humans are a separate from nature, and dominate it, e.g. by treating nature as objects rather than agents with agencies. IPBES understands disconnection in its most encompassing sense, as both emotional as well as physical disconnection (driven by e.g. urbanization or displacement, but also nature conservation measures). The second underlying cause refers to the unequal distribution of wealth and power, that has been increasingly shifted from

public to private actors, with an increasing gap between the Global North and South. This unequal distribution of wealth and power is ultimately leading to biodiversity decline, e.g., through exploitive extraction of natural resources, and nature-detached lifestyles. It is further contributing to the exclusion of less powerful, bottom-up, or marginalized communities from decision-making arenas. The last root cause identified by IPBES concerns the prioritization of short-term, individual and material gains under the assumption of the so-called homo economicus. This root cause manifests for example in economic assessments and incentives or the privatization of public goods and is linked to short term vision in impact assessment, and policies that are tied to election cycles (Gurung et al, 2024).

These three underlying causes further result in concrete challenges to transformative change. The IPBES assessment hereby distinguished five overarching categories, including Persistent relations of domination, Economic and political inequalities; Inadequate policies and unfit institutions; Unsustainable consumption and production patterns, and individual habits and practices; Inaccessible clean technologies and uncoordinated knowledge and innovation systems. Each of these overarching challenges contains sub-challenges, as depicted in Figure 1. As these are all interconnected, achieving transformative change requires a holistic approach that works across several spheres and that can help overcome both underlying causes as well as the several challenges society is facing. Countering those underlying and driving causes of biodiversity loss, and tackling the complex challenges to transformative change is closely linked to the idea of leverage points, as briefly introduced in the following section (Frantzeskaki et al., 2024).

3.2 Opportunities for leverage and upscale

Leverage points can be intuitively understood as those openings in the system where small or big interventions can lead to changes. The leverage points can reach thereby in their transformative potential from shallower to deeper ones (Meadows 1999). Shallower leverage points refer to new practices and material processes closer aligned with deep human-nature relations, also referred to as the 'practical sphere'. Processes aiming for changes of the 'political sphere', the governance structures and rules of the system, represent deeper leverage points, while the deepest leverage points lie in those processes impacting the 'personal sphere', referring to paradigms, worldviews and values overcoming a human-nature distinction (O'Brien 2018). In this deliverable, we interpret opportunities for leverage very broadly as those factors - social, political, economic, ecological or cultural - that facilitate transformative change.

Transformative innovations that can act as leverage points, e.g., through changing practices, governance structures, or worldviews and paradigms, need to be amplified in order to fulfil their full potential. Following Lam et al. 2020 (p3), 'amplification processes describe diverse actions deployed by sustainability initiatives together with other actors (e.g., from government, business, or society) to purposely increase their transformative impact (e.g., initiating a new initiative in another city).' They distinguish three overarching amplification processes, i.e., amplifying within, out, and beyond. *Amplifying within* refers to increasing the impact of one specific initiative or action in the local context, e.g. by stabilising it over the long term or by speeding it up. *Amplifying out* describes processes that increase impact by leaving the initial context and community, and involving other places, such as spreading or replicating a specific initiative elsewhere. *Amplifying beyond*

refers to both a scaling up, that is, achieving change in higher policy scales, and scaling deep by impacting values, worldviews, and broader paradigms (Lam et al. 2020).

Based on Lam et al. (2020)'s extensive literature review, this deliverable is reinterpreting its initial description as opportunities for upscale towards examining in a broader sense amplification process, namely those processes that increase the impact of the biodiversity innovations analysed in the BIOTraCes case studies. We re-interpret this task from upscaling to amplifying based on the literature's critical assessment of upscaling that through a focus on 'solutionism' of scaling often tends to overlook the relational processes required for trust-building, experimentation and co-creation (Pfothenauer, 2021). This is in line with BIOTraCes focus on relationality which can be seen in its understanding of social-ecological systems as systems of complex and interdependent systems of relations (see e.g. BIOTraCes deliverables D1.7 and D2.3).

4 Methodological approach to data analysis

The data sources (interviews and workshops, see Section 2.2) were coded in Nvivo using a mixture of thematic analysis and inductive and deductive coding. We focused thereby, first, on amplification processes and leverage points: amplification processes are understood as processes achieving an increase of impact of the biodiversity innovation, with sub-codes of amplifying within, out, and beyond. Opportunities for leverages were coded according to leverage points at the practices and material level; in the structure, governance, or rules; and paradigms, worldviews, and values.

To explore root causes of biodiversity loss and challenges for transformative change, we used the recent IPBES transformative change assessments' categories as codebook: root causes were coded as underlying causes, indirect and direct drivers, and challenges to transformative change following the five broader categories of persistent relations of domination, economic and political inequalities, inadequate policies and unfit institutions, unsustainable consumption and production patterns, limited access to clean technologies and uncoordinated knowledge and innovation systems. We further added deductively a six category of social and psychological barriers.

5 Results

We now present the results, zooming onto (a) the root causes of biodiversity loss, (b) the challenges and barriers to transformative change that are strongly linked with the root causes, (c) leverage points that reach across the different practical, political, and personal spheres aiming to overcome the root causes and barriers, and (d) amplification processes that already contribute to increase the biodiversity impact locally, across contexts, and through targeting values and world views. These results will be presented in table format, with a small explanation of each underlying framework. We will conclude with a discussion of cross-case findings. Important to note is that the compiled lists of root causes, challenges, leverages and amplification processes by no means is an exhaustive list. Given the context-specific characteristic of each case study, including the different research designs implemented by each consortium partner, case study results developed different emphases on each of the themes analyzed here. While we can see commonalities across all case studies, some findings are also highly context specific. Nonetheless, the following four tables in detail show the interconnectedness across places of current lock-ins and blockages, but also possible pathways towards transformative change.

The tables use the following abbreviations for the case studies: Dutch Foodpark case: NL-FP, Romanian case: RO, Hungarian case: HU, Portuguese case: PT, Lithuanian case: LT, Italian case: IT, Spanish case: ES, Swedish case: SW, Dutch eco-village case NL-EV

5.1 Root causes

The following table depicts the root causes that strongly shape the local social-ecological systems. To transform the multiple social-ecological systems towards just and nature-inclusive systems over the long run, these root causes must be addressed as they lie at the core of the challenges listed in Table 2. The analysis is based on the latest IPBES transformative change assessments (2025) and uses its descriptors of the root causes as code book.

For this end, underlying causes were distinguished into (i) Disconnection from and domination over nature and people, (ii) Concentration of power and wealth, (iii) Prioritization of short-term, individual and material gains. Indirect drivers are distinguished into: (i) Demographic and social-cultural, (ii) Economic and Technological, (iii) Institutions and governance, and (iv) Conflicts and epidemics. Lastly, direct drivers concern (i) Land-use change, (ii) Direct exploitation, (iii) pollution, (iv) climate change, (v) invasive species. Each of these underlying causes were further divided according to BIOTraCes specific findings (see columns "BIOTraCes specification").

Table 1. Root causes of biodiversity loss prevalent in BIOTraCes Case Studies.

IPBES Descriptors	BIOTraCes specification	Examples	Case study
UNDERLYING CAUSES			
Disconnect on from & domination over nature and people	Human-nature dichotomy	Human-nature divide: humans are seen as threat to nature, and at same time also as its stewards. Nature understood as nature conservation areas.	NL-EV
		Agriculture seen as incompatible with nature.	NL-FP
		Educational paradigm driving human separation from nature, hence schoolyards are thought without nature.	ES
		Attachment to human-shaped landscapes, while detaching from river biodiversity	LT
	Modernist/ industrial worldview	Worldview shaped by the Soviet industrial period, where human-made and highly engineered structures like dams were seen as symbols of progress and resilience.	LT
		Modernist worldview prioritizes land development (biodiversity included as an element of design)	NL-FP
		Extractive relationship between conventional farmers and ecosystems.	IT
		Nature as technology (such as energy infrastructure and industrial agriculture)	IT
	Shifting baseline syndrome	Younger generations tend to perceive novel or degraded ecosystems as natural, having no personal memory of earlier, healthier river, forest, or urban landscape conditions	LT/SW/NL-EV/ ES
	Cultural imaginaries	Imaginary of vast plains of large-scale wheat production ignores biodiversity.	PT
		Nature stewards seen as outdated, backward	HU/ NL-EV
		Southern regions constructed as backward areas.	IT
		Traditional agricultural practices based on deep understandings of local landscapes framed as outdated	RO
		Conflicting or lacking perceptions of biodiversity, nature or restoration.	PT/ES/ HU

Concentration of power and wealth	Land and asset control	Land accumulation concentrates power and wealth.	NL-FP/ NL-DB/ RO/ IT/ PT/ HU
		Extractive economic logics drive land use.	PT/ IT/ SW
	Political framing	Biodiversity restoration framed as an extra cost - nature as a luxury	NL-EV/ES
Prioritization of short-term, individual and material gains	Economic utilitarianism	Animals and landscapes viewed as subsidy objects or economic profit	HU/ PT/RO
		Nature's intrinsic value ignored in dam discussions.	LT
		Biodiversity framed as one of many production costs/ expensive project burden	SW/ NL-EV/ES
	Tidiness and efficiency	landscape is valued through its production value (first agriculture, now industries)	NL-AMS
		Tidy-forest norms resist biodiversity restoration.	SW
		Clean schoolyards, that are cost-efficient in maintenance	ES
		Spontaneous plants viewed as weeds or threats.	IT
INDIRECT DRIVERS			
Demographic and social-cultural	Depopulation or rural landscapes	Long-term demographic trend of rural depopulation.	PT/ IT/ RO/ HU
	Aging population	Ageing profession leads to decline in traditional herding practices	HU
	Urban pressure and population density	Housing demand driven by demographic growth in urban areas	NL-EV/ NL-FP/ SW/ (ES)
	Social status and lifestyle	Nature experience reduced to leisure activity.	NL-EV/ ES
Consumerist lifestyles lead to increased living spaces at the cost of nature		NL-EV	
Economic and Technological	Market demands and global trade	Industrial forestry needs (e.g. pulp, paper, timber) drive reforestation trends.	SW
		Economic growth prioritized for city attractiveness.	NL-FP
		Market demands drive agricultural shifts away from subsistence farming towards monocultures (e.g. citrus)	RO/ IT
Institutions and governance	Policy and subsidy failures	Institutional economic focus over landscape and people, which also leads to bureaucracy	HU
		Educational segregation driven by education policies excludes marginalized communities	ES
		Subsidies promote overgrazing which leads to environmental degradation.	RO
	Regulatory burdens and lack of integration	Nature-connected education missing from mainstream policy (PT) or not integrated into learning practices (ES)	PT/ES
		Owners equate biodiversity with externally imposed by authorities	SW
	Planning and Management norms	Sustainability fix: Greenwashing rhetoric in business park development, Wood production framed as enhancing environment.	NL-FP/ SW
Conflicts and epidemics		Business Park/ residential areas expansion justified by necessity.	NL-FP/NL-EV
		Food security concerns driven by Covid and the war in Ukraine prioritize agricultural production and increases pressures on forest land	SW
DIRECT DRIVERS			
Land-use change	Conversion and expansion	Agricultural landscapes (citrus) transformed for industries (photovoltaic and urban production)	IT/ NL-FP
		Urban residential areas expand into forest land.	SW
		Urban densification reduced inner-urban nature.	NL-EV/ ES

		Heathland loss due to forest plantation.	SW
	Intensification and simplification	Historical river regulation dried the landscape or reduced river biodiversity	HU/ LIT
		Agricultural intensification (citrus, even-aged silviculture, cereal monocultures)	NL-FP/ RO /IT/ PT
	Fragmentation	Infrastructure expansion fragments natural forest habitats.	SW
		Habitat fragmentation continues to affect rivers.	LT
		Infrastructure growth and electrical fencing breaks ecological corridors.	RO
	Abandonment	Land abandonment leads to shrub encroachment.	RO
		Abandoned plantations increase wildfire and erosion.	IT
Direct exploitation	Over extraction	Over-extraction and pollution (through agriculture, waste, energy production) impacts river	IT
	Hunting	Overhunting incentivized by policies (e.g. moose perceived as threat)	SW
Climate change		Climate aridity dries soils (also driven by monocultures and overgrazing); desertification risks.	HU/ PT/ IT
		Urban heat island effect leads to loss of local species in inner urban areas	ES
Pollution	Agrochemicals	Chemical use for animal health, Pesticide use sustains industrial citrus production, Nitrogen excess in agriculture	HU/ IT/ NL-EV
	Waste	Waste mismanagement contributes to environmental pollution.	IT
Invasive species		Invasive flora outcompetes native species.	IT/ RO/ PT/ RO/ ES

5.2 Challenges and barriers to transformative change

Challenges to transformative change result from different barriers that are either deeply embedded in our practices, structures and ways of thinking, or that newly - intentionally or unintentionally - arise as contexts change. They are closely linked to the underlying causes and indirect drivers depicted in the table 1. That is, the way we value and relate to biodiversity has a deep impact on the type of measurements we use to assess, the type of policies we implement, the production and consumption models that dominate, or the type of knowledges that inform both our worldviews and everyday practices. To assess them, we draw again on the latest IPBES framework (2024), and the five overarching challenges presented there, together with a categorization of barriers impeding the overcoming of those challenges:

The first challenge of (i) Persistent relations of domination is mirrored in barriers resulting from Categorization and rankings; Measuring, simplifying, & managing; and Justifying resource concentration. The second challenge of (ii) Economic and political inequalities includes the following barriers of Wealth & Power shaping policy; Market pressures / (shareholder) profit overriding public interest; Perceived risks of transformative change. The challenge of (iii) Inadequate policies and unfit institutions materializes e.g. through rigid political and administrative boundaries, uncoordinated institutions and policies, social and ecological cycle mismatches, or understanding and measuring problems of fit. Challenge concerns (iv) Unsustainable consumption and production patterns that are derived from e.g. the Ideology of perpetual growth, Socioeconomic disparities, Telecoupling effects or Ingrained practices and habits. The challenge of (v) Limited access to clean technologies and uncoordinated knowledge and innovation systems manifests for example in Poor availability of sustainability technologies, Ineffective coordination of

knowledge and innovation systems, Inappropriate knowledge transfer and access to sustainable innovations, Unregulated emerging technologies, Marginalization of Indigenous & local knowledge

BIOTraCes findings of the nine case studies spread across all of the five challenges identified by IPBES. That is, the five overarching challenges affect the case studies' niche innovators' capacity to drive and sustain transformative change. Only the barrier of international monetary system constraining political autonomy has not been mentioned in the data analyzed here, which may result on the focus of each case study that centered much more on the local, situated contexts of specific social-ecological systems. Some of the barriers were encountered in nearly all the cases, others were more specific to one or two cases. For some of the barriers, our data pointed to more contextualized differentiations, this can be found in the column of "BIOTraCES specification". We further identified social and psychological barriers as a sixth challenges, as the barriers mentioned there did not map neatly on the five IPBES challenges.

Table 2. Challenges and barriers to transformative change in the BIOTraCes case studies.

IPBES descriptors	BIOTraCes specification (where applicable)	Example	Case study
Persistent relations of domination			
A. Categorization & Rankings	Livestock is mainly seen as a land management tool (tool for nature conservation to keep protected grasslands in good natural condition). or as property that entitles farmers to subsidies.		HU
	Ecological transitions are categorized as "naïve" or "unviable," dismissing niche innovators as "playing at agriculture."		IT
	construction impact sector does not recognize or value alternative human-nature values (including care, tackling loneliness, ...)		NL-EV
	Corporate greenwashing using empty language by incorporating specific nature values to maintain business-as-usual practices.		NL-FP
	Traditional ecological knowledge (TEK) is ranked as "outdated," justifying the exclusion of local communities.		RO
B. Measuring, simplifying, & managing	close (technocratic) definition of biodiversity excludes relational values	Narrow definition of biodiversity undermines the ecological values of Lutkemeer	NL-FP
		Focus on instrumental values of nature (climate change adaptation, nature as learning tool) undermine relational human-nature perspectives of schoolyard	ES
		Technocratisation and juridification favoring legal expertise over alternative knowledge. Every decision in nature management is accompanied by extensive reports prepared by ecological consultancies. Human activities are, by default, considered negative influences. Reduction of nature to a sum of regulated species and habitats governed by government.	NL-EV
		Regional frameworks treating ecological systems as engineering and infrastructure challenges (administrative modus operandi: procurement routines, project funding criteria, and landscape classification systems reflect and reproduce instrumental logics).	PT
	biodiversity loss can easily be compensated	Biodiversity loss is seen as something that can be compensated through certification schemes	SW
		Normalization of environmental damage as an unavoidable cost to be offset by compensation in the construction sector.	NL-EV
C. Justifying resource concentration	Regulatory zoning and permitting processes limiting local influence and alternative territorial visions.	IT	
	Marginalization of subsistence agriculture and small-scale farming in economic policies that favor larger landowners	RO	

	Advocacy for private property rights over environmental regulations by farmers associations. Environmental regulations are perceived as threat to private property	SW	
Economic and political inequalities			
D. Wealth & Power shaping policy	Representation gaps due to lacking self-organization or power imbalances	Lacking self-organization impedes unified opinion and self-representation for pastoralist interests in policymaking.	HU
		Volunteer nature of civic groups restricting capacity to engage or even compete with professional actors.	NL-FP
		Schoolyard greening program as top-down, adult-centric approach creates exclusionary mechanisms for children and marginalized communities	ES
		Poor adherence to legal consultation and participation obligations excluding local input from conservation plans.	RO
	Land concentration by elites and large-scale farmers	Concentration of land ownership enabling elite capture of local economies (citrus monocultures, photovoltaic plants)	IT
		Elite control of territory and adherence to conventional practices reinforced by subsidies (e.g. CAP).	PT
		Inequity in resource access enabling wealthy owners while small farmers struggle to maintain land, increasing land privatization (also driven by CAP structure and requirements that favor large landowners)	RO
	Strategic reframing of bottom-up demands by elites	Resistance to industrialization dismissed as local NIMBYism rather than valid biodiversity concern.	NL-FP
		Political polarization (agricultural land vs. nature conservation) forcing nature initiatives to operate with low visibility to avoid friction.	NL-EV
	Unequal market competition	Open market rules for public land forcing civic initiatives to compete with well-resourced developers.	NL-EV
Delegation of authority to private actors with vested interests	Delegation of land-use decisions to industrial consultants and certification-tied actors.	SW	
F. Market pressures / (shareholder) profit overriding public interest	market pressures erode autonomy of small-scale farmers	Market standardization erodes local autonomy and price resilience. the act of purchasing—largely controlled by retail monopolies—becomes the mechanism through which markets suppress small-scale and diversified production	IT
	financial value determined by the market overrides other locally existent values.	Failure of financial frameworks to grasp the distributive, long-term non-transactional value of the commons. Instead, land resource to be used in the most efficient way, primarily evaluated in financial terms.	NL-FP
		Market preference for large-scale housing projects disadvantaging small nature-positive initiatives.	NL-EV
		marginal, small-scale producers encounter difficulties entering the macro-markets due to poor infrastructure, inadequate branding, and limited marketing channels.	RO
G. Perceived risks of transformative change	Political and financial risk of innovation	political norm to continue decisions from previous city governments combined with the fear of being forced to compensate companies if they would change land-use plans for the disadvantage of the private sector.	NL-EV
		Elderly farmers often encourage their children to pursue other professions than agriculture due to economic insecurities. This dynamic contributes to land abandonment and favors the spread of a “silicon monoculture” which appears to offer older and tired landowners an easy and stable economic return over time.	IT
		Financial insecurity and tight profit margins driving risk aversion among small-scale farmers.	PT
	Fear of the unknown	Rejection of changes in schoolyards due to lacking knowledge regarding its outcomes	ES

		Current biodiversity policies aiming to reverse negative outcomes of previous policies are often met with skepticism by private forest owners, generating a credibility gap that limits the transformative potential of top-down strategies.	SW		
		attachment to current landscapes leads to aversion to changes (even though they may be positive)	LT		
Other	Marginalization of minorities	Systemic marginalization and economic dependency of migrant workers within agro-industrial chains.	IT		
		Dispersed rural geography and territorial disconnection inhibiting participation.	PT		
		Systemic exclusion of ethnic minorities from decision-making and resource allocation.	RO		
Inadequate policies and unfit institutions					
H. Rigid political and administrative boundaries	Misalignment across policy scales or strategies	Top-down governance creating local perception of environmental goals as foreign interests.	LT		
		Regulatory focus on mitigation and nature compensation over human-nature relationship experimentation.	NL-EV		
		National procurement laws emphasizing cost-efficiency over local organic food system support.	PT		
		Rigid European legislation failing to align with or support community-based biodiversity efforts.	RO		
		European commitments to biodiversity protection (EU Biodiversity or River Strategy 2030) are not implemented locally due to the structural weaknesses of local institutions	IT/LT		
		Lack of concrete, supportive EU policy frameworks for highly localized biodiversity innovations.	NL-FP		
		Weak oversight of European funds fostering legal avoidance and stakeholder mistrust.	RO		
	Dependence on EU funding and other financing mechanism (fiscal and budgetary lock-ins)	Chronic underfunding of national environmental budgets leading to dependency on EU financing.	LT		
		Bureaucratic inefficiencies and delayed subsidies burden small-scale farmers	RO		
		municipalities benefitting economically from increasing house construction (tax, land value)	NL-EV		
		Centralization of funding decisions at EU/national levels limiting local influence on incentives.	PT		
		I. Uncoordinated institutions and policies	Sectoral conflicts	Local norms prioritizing infrastructure maintenance over national ecological landscape goals.	LT
				Bottom-up innovations threatened by policies favoring large-scale industrial photovoltaic plants.	IT
				Agricultura sector shows resistance toward national dam removal as they fear negative impacts for their production.	LT
Governance gaps failing to incentivize sustainable practices (such as crop rotation) for large-scale farmers.	RO				
Inflexible nitrogen rules blocking eco-friendly construction while enabling corporate farm buy-outs.	NL-EV				
Unfavorable land restructuring and conversion making pastoral livelihoods impossible.	HU				
Risk of losing income or land control discouraging owners from promoting biodiversity.	SW				
State conservation sees herders as disruptors to conservation efforts; following they are not allowed to intervene in conservation areas.	HU				
Lacking political standards for schoolyard greening on the regional and national level.	ES				
Ruling institutional paradigm promotes individual responsibility and continuity with existing practices goes against efforts to mainstream alternative forestry practices.	SW				

	Institutional inertia and governance fragmentation at the local level	Centralization of power at provincial levels leaving municipalities with little leverage to enact change.	NL-EV
		Too complex local administrative structure with scattered responsibilities and interests makes inter- and intra-institutional collaboration more difficult.	ES
		Not sufficient institutional support for bottom-up initiatives.	ES
		Institutional inertia within municipal structures inhibiting the uptake of regenerative practices.	PT
J. Social and ecological cycle mismatches	Subsidies and the nature conservation regime contribute strongly to inequalities in pasture ownership and use. Restrictions on the time and space of the grazing season are causing increasing financial and natural problems for herders.		HU
	Reliance on fish stocking as a short-term substitute for genuine habitat restoration.		LT
	Local policymakers avoiding divisive ecological issues to prevent community dissatisfaction.		LT
K. Understanding and measuring problems of fit	Reliance on technical agencies using standardized quantitative metrics over situated knowledge.		IT
	Inconsistent mainstreaming and enforcement of nature-inclusive standards in policy.		NL-EV
Unsustainable consumption and production patterns			
L. The ideology of perpetual growth	Global value chain capture of local agricultural economic value.		IT
	Land speculation: investors buying lands that is potentially to develop in future, driving prices up.		NL-EV
	Systemic conflict between ecological restoration and economic growth.		NL-EV/FP
	Real estate speculation increases development pressures on forest lands close to urban areas.		SW
M. Socioeconomic disparities	Difficulties in accessing financial capital due to generational economic lock-ins.		NL-EV
N. Telecoupling effects	Industrial preference for export-oriented trade over local food networks		HU
	Telecoupling effects of high-intensity import-export food regimes.		NL-FP
	International meat demand driving local pasture overexploitation.		RO
	International market pressures and price spikes driving local forest extraction (e.g. war in Ukraine)		SW
O. Ingrained practices and habits	Soil fertility is treated as a resource to be exploited for productivity		IT
	Standardized production models incentivizing chemical inputs and monocultures.		PT/SW
	Historical Swedish forestry debates locking in clear-cutting as the primary paradigm.		SW
	Certification standards allowing retention for conservation primarily on unproductive land, allowing owners to maintain productive forestry on the more economically valuable parts of their properties leading in turn to homogeneity of environmental values in the forest.		SW
Limited access to clean technologies and uncoordinated knowledge and innovation systems			
P. Poor availability of sustainability technologies	Banking sector unfamiliarity with collective mortgages blocking housing finance.		NL-EV
Q. Ineffective coordination of knowledge and innovation systems	Lack of recognition for bottom-up monitoring undermining biodiversity data.		IT
	Ecological assessments of rivers presented in formal, inaccessible formats for residents. Scientific data remaining within academic circles, inaccessible to local authorities.		LT
	Reliance on technical models overshadowing practical ecological insight (e.g. nitrogen)		NL-EV
	Bureaucratic certification systems poorly adapted to small-scale forestry.		SW

R. Inappropriate knowledge transfer and access to sustainable innovations	lacking knowledge transfer to younger generations or niche innovators	Elderly farmers passing on intensive agricultural techniques as the primary legacy.	IT
		Exclusionary technical planning procedures requiring years of specialized study.	NL-EV
		Generational divides challenging the transmission of traditional ecological knowledge.	RO/HU
		Individual forest owners adopting a passive role due to a lack of alternative knowledge.	SW
	Knowledge gaps of decision-making and funding acquisition	Local actors have knowledge gaps in national and EU decision-making and funding acquisition hindering local implementation.	HU/PT
S. Unregulated emerging technologies	Technological advances (e.g. electric fences) in husbandry minimizing human presence and herding knowledge.		HU/RO
	Top-down techno-fixes for irrigation exacerbating the marginalization of smallholders.		IT
T. Marginalization of Indigenous & local knowledge	Marginalization of the essential ecological and culinary knowledge of elderly women.		PT
	Traditional grazing knowledge overlooked or symbolically included in governance.		RO/HU
Social and psychological barriers			
Social and psychological barriers	(lacking) public awareness and emotional attachments outweighing scientific evidence for restoration.		LT
	Politicized communication and distrust in the interests behind ecological debates.		LT
	Participation fatigue resulting from the overwhelming number of issues for local groups.		PT
	Lack of leadership and individual hesitation to engage in transdisciplinary platforms or drive community-level action		RO/LT
	Opposition to schoolyard greening is rising due to safety risks, hygiene concerns, and fears that multi-purpose spaces might limit physical activity.		ES

5.3 Leverage points

BIOTraCes' case studies explore biodiversity innovations across four sectors of agriculture, forestry, urbanisation, and water systems. In these cases, local communities aim to change current ways of doing and thinking, either by implementing new practices or by pushing forward alternative ideas and paradigms. Despite the different levels of each of these cases - some are more at the initial community- and trust building phase, others already draw on decades-long action - all these case work with different leverages to alter the social-ecological system. These leverages work across the three spheres of transformation, classified by O'Brien and Sygna (2013), which has also been taken up in the recent IPBES transformative change assessment. According to these three spheres, leverages can act from shallower to deeper reaching levels at (i) the practical sphere, (ii) the political sphere concerning structures, governance, or rules, or (iii) at the personal sphere changing dominant worldviews and value systems towards being more attentive to closer human-nature relations.

Table 3. Leverage points prevalent in the BIOTraCes case studies.

Category	Sub-category	BIOTraCes examples
Practical sphere: practices & ecological processes		
		ES: Urban heat islands triggering rethinking of schoolyards

D3.1 Opportunities for leverage and upscaling

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Ecological processes	Natural processes requiring adaptation	PT & IT: Desertification triggering rethinking of agricultural model
		HU: Traditional herding as essential to maintain grassland ecosystems
Alternative economic practices	Creating economic infrastructure and markets for more sustainable livelihoods	RO: Promoting sustainable tourism and local traditional products, e.g., through village festivals selling local products from sustainable agriculture
		SW: Developing local infrastructure and markets for high-quality timber.
		IT: Renewable energy communities as a collective and local alternative to dependencies on big energy companies
		IT: Simeto Bio-district - a network of small organic farmers
		PT: Mértola Food Network
	Nature-connected & small-scale production practices	IT & PT: Agroecological production, e.g. through crop-diversification, short supply chains, and restoration of agricultural land through syntropic farming or permaculture
Research practices & use of knowledge	Co-producing evidence base of social-ecological change for decision-making	IT: collaborative mapping of photovoltaic plants to make visible the scale, distribution, and socio-ecological impacts of industrial photovoltaic installations across the Valley
	Research workshops as spaces of dialogue enabling community building	ES: Space for educational communities to voice their opinions with municipal actors
		SE: Space for dialogue between forest owners on alternative forestry as first contact point
	Research activity as catalyst for awareness raising	LT: Research activity, e.g., interviews, to bring the local community's attention to the importance of river renaturalisation
	Leveraging scientific knowledge	PT: Creating a research centre to support innovation in biodiversity loss control
		ALL: using BIOTraCes outcomes as a form to leverage local biodiversity innovations
	Enabling knowledge exchange	PT: The development agency ESDIME facilitates farmer-to-farmer exchange
		ES: the city hall organises conferences to exchange knowledge and practices regarding schoolyard transformations
IT: Farmers are exchanging with experts regarding alternative agricultural practices		
HU & PT: Passing ecological knowledge from older to younger generations		
	NL-EV: The province is providing toolboxes and material regarding nature-inclusive building	
Successful practices as inspiration for others to follow	Successfully implemented initiatives serve as inspiration for others to follow	NL-FP: potential: Winning the public tender (although for a much smaller area than planned) as inspiration for others to follow
		ES: A successful bottom-up schoolyard transformation in one of the city's schools has motivated other schools to follow
		ES: Successful municipal schoolyard greening programs from other cities, e.g. Barcelona, has inspired the municipal pilot program
		NL-EV: Potential: the collective land acquisition can set the path for other similar initiatives to follow
Changing educational practices	Learning in nature to shift mindsets & capacities to address biodiversity loss	PT: School gardens shifting children's perceptions of agricultural production
		ES: Project-based learning in green schoolyards as a means to foster systems thinking and collaborative decision-making
Political sphere: Structure, governance, rules		

Supportive legal frameworks & policy tools	Embedding biodiversity innovation in legal frameworks across scales	LT: European Water framework directive and biodiversity strategy as a top-down enabler for local renaturalisation efforts such as renaturalisation of rivers
		NL-EV: Clashes between ambitious European and national (anti-) restoration goals as anchoring points for local innovation. De Beuk embedding local innovation in European Goals as a leverage against national policies
		ES: Embedding sustainability and new forms of embodied learning in national education laws and curriculum
		NL-EV: Creation and testing of municipal tools that provide the legal framework for biodiversity innovations to be implemented, such as the CPO policy
		NL-EV: POTENTIAL: Private building sector demanding from policymakers a rating system for including nature-inclusivity in building programs, so that developers' efforts are recognised and lead to some benefits. This would further enable an easier integration through the creation of specific indicators
		NL-EV: Creation of a biodiversity policy programs at the province level, such as the Community of Practice that provides grants to smaller local initiatives
		ES: Creation of a municipal schoolyard greening pilot program enabling schoolyard renaturalisation of 14 schools
Plural knowledge in decision-making	Integration of traditional/ local knowledge into decision-making	PT: Recognising lay people's knowledge in municipal decision-making has played pivotal role in changing the municipal mentality
		RO: POTENTIAL leveraging traditional ecological knowledge as potential base for policymaking
		HU: Upscaling traditional knowledge by researchers to inform national and European policy-making
Collaborations between institutional & non-institutional actors	Supportive institutions - Collaborations with authorities	LT: Recognition of biodiversity challenges at the national level translate into political support (e.g., funding or policy support) for biodiversity innovation locally
		NL-FP: Local authorities starting to recognise biodiversity innovations, e.g. Amsterdam's donut economy approach reflects to an extent the social-ecological vision of Foodpark Amsterdam
		PT: Reducing economic risk involved in biodiversity innovation by providing support (funding, training) to make the shift towards more regenerative agriculture
		ES: POTENTIAL- Setting standards for green schoolyards at the municipal level
	Co-governance based on meaningful participation	PT: Co-governance between municipality and relevant actors leading to improved management of SES
Institutional niche innovators	Niche innovators challenging institutional dynamics from within	IT: Eco-museum as the outcome of a process of co-governance
		NL-EV: civil servants of the province navigating institutional dynamics to pursue biodiversity goals
		ES: civil servants of the city-hall employing various strategies to funding and prolongation of the municipal schoolyard greening pilot program
Bottom-up niche innovators	Innovations to overcome structural barriers	NL-EV, an association, started a landscape cooperative as cooperatives can acquire land, while associations cannot. This is to facilitate the collective land acquisition
		IT: Renewable energy communities as laboratories
	Bottom-up organisation, community, and network building	ES: Collective manifesto of all municipal parents' associations and school to demand changes for educational environments from the city hall
		SW: Collaboration between forest owners to exchange services needed for continuous cover forestry and push for change in organisations
		PT: Creating a food network to reduce dependence on external purchase

Shifts in governments	New governments allow new discourses to emerge	NL's change in government shifted discourse from anti-nature towards one more inclusive of environmental policies.
Personal sphere: imaginaries & values		
Imaginary shifts	Changing the imaginary of the territory	<p>IT: Shifting from modernist narrative of territory as underdeveloped to a relational narrative of the territory rooted in its history and culture</p> <p>PT: landscape with no future reframed to 'territory of regeneration'</p> <p>NL-FP: reframing Lutkemeer as a place enabling consumerism towards one centred on its biodiversity and the community</p>
	Challenging paradigms by creating social-ecological and locally rooted imaginaries and framing local initiatives as an alternative towards high impact sector 'wrongs'	NL-FP: Foodpark Amsterdam as a model of moving from extractivist, neoliberal to relational economic paradigms (e.g. the commons), by showing shortcomings of current economic paradigm (current model fails to support socio-ecological wellbeing)
		NL-EV: Reframing nature from being a barrier (human vs nature) towards being a benefit and part of social systems. E.g. Nature not as an additional cost in the building sector, but as an integral part of building. The province also up took 'health' as an objective in their policy program, as this is more likely to be approved and supported in the current political climate than nature on its own
		NL-EV: large scale housing developments vs. small scale ecovillage; falsify the usual assumption that sustainable building in close harmony with nature is more expensive than using mainstream materials and procedures
		ES: Emerging shifts from a modernist towards a relational educational paradigm in national laws and in local framings of schoolyard greening that include care and stewardship
		ES: Approaching schoolyard greening through three holistic goals of the renaturalised schoolyard's contribution to achieving sustainability, co-education and inclusivity
		IT: Challenging dominant sector paradigms, e.g. small-scale agroecological production vs. industrialised mono-cultures, or renewable energy communities vs. monopolised large-scale photovoltaic power plants
		PT: Regenerative farming as a way to counter agricultural practices driving desertification
	SE: Continuous cover forestry vs. monoculture forests	
	Research activity bringing marginalised human-nature relations to the fore	<p>IT: PAR led to a reinterpretation of traditional fishing and livestock practices, reframing them as important components of the local SES</p> <p>ES: multi-actor workshops gave space for relational perspectives of schoolyard greening to emerge</p>
Values	Leveraging relational values	SW: People holding cultural and relational values attached to forests as a potential driver of transforming current extractivist practices
		ES. Green schoolyards as relational places that strengthen practices and sentiments of care and stewardship
		RO: Connection of oak trees with identity leveraging activities to protect them
		IT: Building upon an already existing sense of place and community in the Simeto Valley to amplify local initiatives
		IT: Activities and practices implemented by the eco-museum as a way to strengthen relational values
	Generational change brings new values and	<p>SE: Succession as opportunities for alternative ideas on forestry</p> <p>PT & RO: Youths returning to rural areas and bringing biodiversity innovations</p>

can hence lead to new innovations

HU: Opening a herder school to enable younger generations access to traditional knowledge and to keep it for the future.

5.4 Amplification processes

A process that is amplifying the biodiversity innovation is a process that contains actions with the purpose to increase the innovation's impact locally, across contexts, or on deeper-lying worldviews and values, i.e., they aim to spread those actions, practices and initiatives that contribute towards achieving a just and nature-inclusive future across time and space (Lam et al. 2020).

The following table shows those amplification processes that are already happening or that hold great potential to be implemented in future, as identified by consortium partners and that aim to overcome those challenges, barriers, and root causes listed in table 1 and 2. Those amplification processes can broadly be clustered into amplifying within, out, and beyond following Lam et al. (2020). We expanded this classification with subcategories specific to the BIOTraCes case studies.

Table 4. Amplification processes happening within, out, and beyond the BIOTraCes case studies' local contexts.

Amplifying how?	Increasing impact through:	BIOTraCes examples
Within (the local context)...		
... through creating awareness and community surrounding the local innovation.	Creating awareness and spreading word about the biodiversity innovation locally.	SW: Slowly building community by bringing together individual actors through research activities, LT: Creating a community by sharing, communicating about the river renaturalization.
	Co-producing local knowledge: Researchers as trustworthy knowledge brokers and facilitators within the local community.	LT: Amplifying plural voices: collecting existing local perspectives of the river from community members as a starting point to create awareness and open space for discussions locally, as first step trust-building. IT: Co-creating and sharing a social-ecological mapping of photovoltaic plants by involving local actors in the data collection and visualization.
	Celebrating small wins and communication success stories (Energising - Termeer & Dewulf 2019).	NL-EV: Celebration of small wins that help De Beuk get closer to their goal of building an eco-village, also to maintain motivation and to communicate innovation to local communities.
	Creating local economic infrastructure and markets.	RO: sustainable tourism and branding of local products at local festivals, IT & PT: food and farmers networks, SW: Promoting high quality timber production.
	Campaigning for the biodiversity innovation.	ES: bottom-up schoolyard transformation project campaigning for neighborhood votes in the annual municipal participatory budget contest.
... through deepened multi-actor collaborations.	Creating local communities, networks, and synergies that share goals of transformative change.	SW: Communication and network building between forest owners interested in alternative practices. ES: Collective manifesto signed by all municipal public schools demanding the transformation of school environments and increased perception of importance of the biodiversity innovation. IT: Co-creation and management of social-ecological map and its database AND co-creation of Eco-museum diversifies actors involved and grows knowledge regarding biodiversity challenge within the local context.

		<p>IT: Sharing own micro strategies of regenerative agriculture with other farmers and experts in the region helps to grow knowledge regarding alternative agricultural practices.</p> <p>HU: Connecting traditional herders to initiate knowledge exchange and to create a herders community.</p>
	Collaborating with local authorities/ increasing institutional recognition of the biodiversity innovation.	<p>HU: Researchers collect data regarding immunization of foxes from diverse actors, incl. hunters & institutions, to share it with low-and mid-level authorities, so they communicate with higher level authorities.</p> <p>ES: Presenting the collective manifesto for school transformations to the city hall led to the formulation of a municipal schoolyard greening pilot program.</p> <p>NL-FP: Winning a public tender for a plot of land that allows Foodpark Amsterdam to develop a part of their project.</p> <p>NL-EV: Collaborating with the municipality to advance and test policy tools that could set a precedent for future actions, such as the Collective Private Commissioning policy.</p>
	Niche innovators advocating for biodiversity innovation from within the institutions	<p>ES: municipal technical staff advocating inside the city hall for prolongation of schoolyard greening pilot program.</p> <p>NL-EV: civil servants at the province creating novel policy programs for biodiversity.</p>
<p>... through learning by doing (Termeer & Dewulf 2019).</p>	Agroecological experimentation.	<p>IT: Experimenting with different alternatives to monoculture</p> <p>NL-FP: Experimenting with commons-based approaches to agriculture</p> <p>IT & PT: Experimenting with agricultural techniques to regenerate the soil</p>
	Pedagogical experimentation.	ES: Creating and sharing materials & methodologies with teachers for the use of denaturalized schoolyards in curricular and extracurricular activities
<p>... through stabilising and speeding up (by doing the same biodiversity innovation longer or faster) (Lam et al., 2020).</p>	Implementing pilots until they stabilise (logic of attraction - Termeer & Dewulf 2019)	<p>ES: From pilots to long-lasting programs: Replicating schoolyard greening in several schools, to achieve a critical mass showing the positive impact of the biodiversity innovations.</p> <p>NL-EV: De Beuk is applying to become a pilot for Nitrogen-free building, setting a precedent for nature-inclusive building close to nature reservoirs, showing that living in harmony with nature can be possible.</p>
	Integrating the biodiversity innovations into day-to-day practices to increase communities' capacities to enact change.	<p>ES: Using schoolyards in teaching and recreational activities, normalizing children's contact with nature as an integral part of the educational day-to-day.</p> <p>IT & PT: Micro strategies of regenerative agriculture, e.g. new ways of using water</p>
	Creation of municipal tools that enable replication of the biodiversity innovations.	NL-EV & ES: Experimentation and implementation with municipal tools, such as the CPO policy or a municipal schoolyard greening program.
Out (to other places and communities)...		

<p>... through building networks across different places and communities.</p>	<p>Participation in policy and civil society networks, to enable knowledge exchange.</p>	<p>ES: City-hall organizing conferences and participating in city networks to exchange about schoolyard greening programs and initiatives. NL-EV: Participation in a vast number of networks, e.g. the one of ecovillages, including diverse actor groups. HU: Connecting with traditional herders across the globe, e.g. by participating in the International Year of Rangelands and Pastoralists.</p>
<p>... by spreading (Lam et al., 2020).</p>	<p>Building education programs that teach traditional knowledge</p>	<p>HU: establishing herder schools that enable younger generation's access to traditional knowledge while also fostering innovations, following examples of schools in Spain.</p>
	<p>Transdisciplinary dissemination and communication (by combining arts and culture with biodiversity actions)</p>	<p>IT & RO & HU: Traditional festivals selling local products and showcasing local traditions. HU: Slow films following a day of herder on YouTube that reached a broad audience. IT: Exhibitions showing the history of the rivers and the community which then turned into a mechanism of networking with other Eco-museums. LT: Designing and using games together with the local communities where participants could write down their wishes for the local river. NL-FP: Dutch architecture biennial where Foodpark Amsterdam presented their initiative through a short film in collaboration with the Twente team. ES & NL-EV: Creating toolboxes and setting standards in how to put biodiversity innovations into practice, e.g., toolboxes for integrating schoolyards in the teaching or for integrating nature in building practices.</p>
	<p>Researchers communicate traditional knowledge's importance to higher scale policy levels.</p>	<p>HU: upscaling traditional knowledge through researchers acting as knowledge communicators on the higher policy scales.</p>
<p>... by replicating and transferring (Lam et al.).</p>	<p>Exchanging and replicating traditional practices and knowledge with other regions</p>	<p>PT & IT: learning and implementing regenerative agriculture practices from other places (syntropic farming, permaculture) PT: Transferring syntropic agricultural techniques outside of Portugal through volunteering and refugee programs HU: Sharing of and learning from traditional herders' knowledge around the world</p>
	<p>Disseminating scientific knowledge about the biodiversity innovation</p>	<p>ALL: Using BIOTraCes activities and results to increase legitimacy of biodiversity innovation by communicating results with communities and policymakers.</p>
	<p>Sharing and replicating locally successful innovations with other regions (Bandwagon effect - Termeer & Dewulf 2019)</p>	<p>IT: Using counter-mapping tools, such as social-ecological mapping of energy production, in other contexts. PT: Neighboring municipalities replicating syntropic farming practices and being inspired by Mértola's vision ES: Conferences where pioneer municipalities or regions share experiences of schoolyard greening initiatives RO: Expanding eco-tourism activities in the region, expanding local festivals that promote sustainable agriculture</p>
	<p>Potential: Setting an example by successfully implementing</p>	<p>NL-FP: Community land trusts NL-EV: collective private commissioning of the municipality of Wageningen</p>

	ambitious policies, to replicate them in other places.	ES: Municipal schoolyard greening program with fixed annual budget
... beyond (towards governance structures and worldviews, paradigms) ...		
...by scaling up through changing rules (Lam et al., 2020).	Influencing and/or changing legislation & regulations	ES: New national education law proposing alternative education models as an opportunity for shifting education paradigms (coupling - Termeer & Dewulf 2019) LT: EU water directive that requires renaturalization of rivers implemented by national governments NL-EV: Potential: Adapting residential permitting processes to accommodate nature-positive lifestyle choices, e.g., electric-only vehicles, prohibition of fireplaces, and pesticide-free gardening. If residents were willing to comply with such conditions, they could be permitted to live closer to protected natural areas
... by scaling deep through changing values (Lam et al., 2020).	Amplifying new human perspectives of nature (including human dependency on nature)	NL-EV: New narrative of nature-positive living in the De Beuk project. IT: Showing the history of human-nature relationships in a museum exhibition, changing relationships with the territory.
	Shifting imaginaries around biodiversity in policy, society, and economy.	ES: Potential: Integrating emerging relational perspectives of schoolyards into policy framings, e.g., by attaching an overarching narrative of schoolyard greening to practices of care. NL-EV: connecting nature-inclusivity with other discourses, e.g. health, to increase recognition of the challenge.
... by showcasing successful and scalable examples that prove change is possible.	Embedding regenerative practices aligned with sustainable ways of living in & from the territory.	IT: Replacing intensive agriculture with permaculture along the river, embedding historic social-ecological relations. PT: syntropic farming to regenerate the soil and provide sustainable agriculture to the local community. SW: forest owners lobbying together at forest owners' organizations to give counselling on continuous cover forestry and creating new infrastructure that supports these practices. NL-FP: Potential: Community land trust as alternative landownership model to privatization; Changing economic paradigm at municipality level (Doughnut Economy; commons agenda). ES: Potential: Mainstreaming schoolyard greening as the norm, not the exception. NL-FP: Potential: Mainstreaming nature-inclusive building as the norm.

5.5 Cross-cutting results

Root causes of biodiversity loss

An analysis of the root causes of biodiversity loss that shape the local social-ecological systems examined in the BIOTraCes case studies shows that the root of the root of current lock-ins in the system lie in the predominant disconnection from nature and the perception of human domination over nature. Those become visible in production and consumption behaviors, through top-down policies favoring productivity and/or nature conservation over closer human-nature relations, a modernist paradigm that drives disconnection from nature, or through the shifting baseline syndrome that shows how especially younger

generations perceive highly degraded ecosystems as the normal state of the social-ecological systems in the Lithuanian, Swedish, Dutch ecovillage, or Spanish case.

The disconnection and domination become also apparent through dominant narratives that frame social processes and ecological systems as incompatible, such (human-driven) agriculture or housing developments vs. nature conservation (the Dutch cases), a top-down education program that views embodiment with nature as constraining learning outcomes (Spanish cases), or attachment to human-engineered landscapes overriding natural river landscapes (Lithuanian case). This is further driven by cultural imaginaries that frame alternative practices based on local and traditional knowledge or rural areas with communities living in closer relationship with nature as outdated or backwards. In addition, many of the case studies deal with increasing concentration of power and wealth, either in form of landownership that concentrates market power in a few large-scale farmers while marginalizing small-scale and subsistence farmers (e.g. in the Romanian, Italian, Hungarian, or Portuguese case) or in industrial, forestry and construction companies accumulating extractivist power over local, community-led initiatives as can be seen in both Dutch and in the Swedish cases. The cases further have in common that nature or biodiversity is often understood in utilitarian terms, leading to a financial evaluation of nature's benefits. Biodiversity is here in parts approached as a cost-intensive object/ extra-cost (see e.g. the Spanish case or the Dutch ecovillage case) or seen through its production values (e.g. in agriculture).

These underlying causes described in the previous paragraph create indirect drivers of biodiversity loss, that is, mechanisms prevalent in the economic, social-cultural, institutional and other processes. In the BIOTraCes cases, these indirect drivers materialize for instance in depopulation processes of rural areas, due to lacking economic opportunities, aging populations, or dominating narratives of rural areas as marginal (as seen in the Portuguese, Italian, Romanian, and Hungarian cases), resulting on the other hand in urban population growth with severe impacts on urban and peri-urban biodiversity (such as in the two Dutch, the Swedish, or the Spanish case to a smaller degree). Indirect drivers can also be seen in policy and subsidy failures that, while some are indeed well-intended, promote practices misaligned with transformative change agendas. Examples are here subsidies promoting overgrazing or overproduction in agricultural or forest landscape (Hungarian, Swedish, or Romanian case), or educational systems driving educational segregation (Spanish case), or urban development policies directly driving biodiversity loss by justifying action through the necessity of societies for housing and industrial activity (the two Dutch cases).

These indirect drivers strengthen direct drivers of biodiversity loss, including land-use changes, e.g. by shifting from agricultural to industrial activities (in the Dutch foodpark or the Italian case), by intensifying agricultural activity (such as through citrus or wheat production in the Italian and Portuguese case), simplifying river landscapes (Lithuanian case) or by fragmenting important biodiversity habitats, such as for example in the Swedish, Lithuanian or Romanian case. Land-use changes further lead to direct exploitation; BIOTraCes findings for example point to practices of overgrazing or hunting, and an increasing environmental degradation through pollution using chemicals and pesticides in husbandry and agriculture, or waste mismanagement.

Overall, the analysis of root causes that drive biodiversity loss in the BIOTraCes social-ecological systems shows the complex interplay of underlying causes derived from nature-detached or dominating worldviews that contribute to a marginalization of biodiversity

innovations in the public discourse and in many policy making processes. Resulting, current economic practices that shape the local systems, combined with insufficient or counterproductive governance processes lead to direct drivers of biodiversity loss, visible through land-use changes driven by a productivist and extractivist logic, through exploitation of natural resources, or the increasing impacts of climate change. These root causes further lead to lock-ins and create challenges for transformative change that will be described in the following section.

Challenges and barriers to transformative change

IPBES identified in its latest transformative change assessment five overarching challenges that currently limit the transformative potential of shifting practices, institutions and governance frameworks, and worldviews and values towards just and nature-inclusive outcomes. Those challenges are closely linked to the underlying causes of biodiversity loss and manifest through persistent relations of domination, economic and political inequalities, inadequate policies and unfit institutions, unsustainable production and consumption patterns, and the marginalization of plural knowledge systems. Our findings further point to a sixth challenge that can broadly be described as social and psychological barriers, including lacking public awareness and emotional attachments to biodiversity issues and landscapes, politicized debates about environmental issues that lead to a disconnect of local communities, participation fatigue of community actors that are lacking the time and often the financial power to engage in and drive transformative change locally, and in some parts also lacking local leadership that is needed to mobilize and amplify local community efforts.

Due to the extensive list of challenges encountered in the BIOTraCes cases (see Table 2), we now focus on a few interesting observations: most of the cases show the tendency to assess biodiversity through a technocratic and sectoralized approach. This leads to a strict separation of the human and more-than-human actors, as most visible in those cases where nature can seemingly only be preserved if no human intervenes (e.g. the Hungarian or Dutch ecovillage case), or in those cases where biodiversity is treated as an exploitable object, e.g. through large-scale and mono-cultural agriculture, forest, and industrial activity (e.g. the Romanian, Hungarian, Swedish, Italian, Portuguese case). It further leads to the assumption that biodiversity loss can easily be compensated, e.g. financially, as shows the policy to offset nitrogen or certification schemes in the Swedish forestry sector. Often, biodiversity is merely understood through its instrumental value, such as contributor to climate change adaptation or improved learning outcomes of children in the Spanish case. All these examples show how closer human-nature relationships are overrun by technocratic approaches to categorize, measure, simplify and manage biodiversity in diverse social-ecological systems. The marginalization of relational approaches in social-ecological governance is thereby closely linked to the underlying root cause of human disconnection from nature and the dominant worldview that considers humans as superior to nature.

The BIOTraCes biodiversity innovations are further challenged by the multi-level governance structure that reaches in the most cases from the most local municipal governance toward the European scale. Nearly all the cases describe difficulties derived from this structure, whereby biodiversity-supportive European policies are limited in their local impact, either through their detachment from local contexts and realities, through their still persistent economic focus prioritizing productivity, or through institutional inertias at the local level that difficult a real implementation of European policies. In some case

this is further accelerated by a dependency on European funding and subsidy mechanisms leading to power imbalance between political actors and local communities. This also impedes the implementation of transformative experimentation locally, as communities and local actors need to respond to funding requirements formulated elsewhere. That is, BIOTraCes findings point to severe shortcomings of the multi-level governance structure for transformative change.

Lastly, the case studies point to a lacking integration of plural knowledge systems and to knowledge gaps of local community actors regarding decision-making processes. That is, many cases such as the Romanian or Hungarian one show how traditional knowledge holders remain marginalized through their exclusion from decision-making processes. This leads to policies that are disconnected from the challenges specific to each social-ecological system, and overruns innovations that can lead to transformations in the systems. Marginalized actors often lack the knowledge or encounter difficulties in accessing political arenas, or in funding acquisition that requires lengthy technical reports and complex bureaucratic processes out of reach for small-scale businesses or farmers. This leads to a systemic exclusion of important niche innovators. However, their voices and expertise are of utmost importance for driving transformative change towards a nature-inclusive future.

Despite the multiple root cause, challenges and barriers that result in systemic lock-ins, the BIOTraCes case show many positive examples of strategies, actions, and initiatives taken by a variety of actor groups at the local scale. The following section will dive into those processes that can be considered important leverage points, supporting the innovations and their driving actors towards achieving far-reaching impact.

Leverage points

At the practice level, a leverage point encountered in several of the case studies refers to the creation of alternative local economy structures that allow communities to gain an income through different biodiversity innovations, e.g., by building up a sustainable tourism sector, developing local infrastructures around agriculture and energy, and creating networks of local businesses employing small-scale and sustainable production and consumption practices. At the practice level, we further identify processes aiming for the creation of spaces of dialogue that allow for community- and trust-building a key leverage point and main condition for transformations to appear and take shape. Here, the research activities implemented under BIOTraCes and following a participatory action research approach have been considered in some cases as a crucial momentum supporting the creation of awareness locally for the biodiversity challenge and the emergence of local and traditional knowledge and values of diverse community members.

Leverage points occurring at the political sphere and constituting a window of opportunity to change the governance context are, for instance, already existing legal frameworks and policy tools supportive of transformative biodiversity innovations. Those can imply European directives and visions, such as the EU Water framework directive or the EU nature restoration law (relevant for the Lithuanian), or take the form of national laws, such as the latest Spanish education law that puts sustainability and project-based learning at its heart (relevant to the Spanish case), or concern ambitious policies and tools developed and implemented at the regional and municipal scale, such as a regional biodiversity program in the Dutch Province case, municipal collective private commissioning policies or community land trusts that enable collective land acquisition (both Dutch cases), or the implementation of a municipal schoolyard greening pilot program (as in the Spanish case).

Those policy tools across scale are key leverages for local innovation, as they allow local initiatives to be embedded in broader policy visions and hence create legitimacy of the innovation.

In the political sphere, next to these top-down processes, the role of bottom-up movements is crucial. In cases where institutional actors are supportive of local biodiversity innovation, collaborations involving local authorities, civil society, and in some parts also economic actors have been found key leverage points as they allow for alternative practices to occur. Collaborations can take the form of community actors receiving financial support by institutional actors or of co-governance and meaningful participation in decision-making processes regarding the future of the territory. In those BIOTraCes cases, where institutional support of the local biodiversity innovation is absent, bottom-up community- and network-building and collective organisation has been crucial for the biodiversity innovation to occur. This, for instance, includes the creation of renewable energy communities by local residents in the Italian case, local food networks in the Portuguese case, or the writing of a collective manifesto presenting community demands to the city hall in the Spanish case.

Leverage points situated in the personal sphere are those that can reach the deepest as they change paradigms, worldviews and values informing both the political and practical sphere. In the BIOTraCes cases, we identify processes leveraging both alternative imaginaries and values. Leveraging new social-ecological and locally rooted imaginaries is occurring, for instance, by framing local initiatives as an alternative towards high impact sector 'wrongs'. In some of the BIOTraCes cases, this even supported the creation of new, positive imaginaries of the territory needed to overcome a human-nature disconnection. For instance, local initiative's imaginaries are countering dominant sector paradigms, e.g. small-scale agroecological and forest production vs. industrialised mono-cultures (in the Portuguese, Italian and Swedish cases), renewable energy communities vs. monopolised large-scale photovoltaic power plants (in the Italian case), nature-positive ecovillages vs. large-scale housing developments (in the Dutch eco-village case), or a Commons- and nature-based society vs. one centred on consumerism (in the Dutch Foodpark case). Following, imaginaries that describe territories and landscapes as underdeveloped, without future, or little ecological value can be re-framed towards those challenging broader paradigms, while also offering sustainable alternatives for local communities.

Amplification processes

In terms of amplifying within the local context, we find a lot of relational processes such as building trust and networks, also through the celebration of small wins, necessary for bottom-up movements to grow into biodiversity interventions. Crucially, these involve a lot of experimentation, highlighting the need for context-dependent solutions instead of the replication and scaling of preexisting uniform policy solutions. Multi-actor collaborations, especially between institutional and community actors are key to achieve a stabilisation of the biodiversity innovation over the long term. The testing of innovative policy tools, such as collective private commissioning, can thereby play a core role in embedding the biodiversity innovation into institutional structures. Niche innovators inside institutional structures can thereby act as important facilitators translating the biodiversity innovations' goals into policy program.

To increase the biodiversity innovation's impact beyond the local context, namely amplifying out towards reaching other communities and places, amplifying mechanisms

include the participation of local actors in diverse networks, including civil society, policy, and multi-actor networks. The participation in cross-scale networks enables the sharing of locally created knowledge and experiences with other similar actors to replicate successful practices elsewhere or the advocating for new policy tools that could facilitate the successful implementation of the biodiversity innovation's goal, such as collective land acquisition mechanisms.

Many of the BIOTraCes case studies further draw on transdisciplinary dissemination and communication. By combining artistic tools of communication with scientific knowledge, e.g. through museum exhibitions or films visualising local social-ecological histories, the biodiversity innovation can more easily be communicated to a broader audience, leading to increased awareness across multiple actors. Lastly, bandwagon effects (Termeer & Dewulf 2019) are highlighted in many of the cases, where the success of local innovation can be seen in biodiversity innovations being replicated in other places. While these are so far often potentials that are seen for upscaling, such as the possible expansion of eco-tourism in the Romanian case, or the wider adoption of community land trusts and collective private commissioning in the Dutch Foodpark case and Dutch eco-village case, there are several examples where biodiversity interventions have already inspired the replication in other places. Those are to be found for instance in the Portuguese case where more neighboring municipalities to Mértola are implementing syntropic farming techniques, or the increase in schoolyard greening programs in a European context.

Lastly, the case studies show how changing legislation on higher policy scales can amplify local innovative practices. In some cases, the biodiversity issue is already directly addressed at the highest policy levels, such as the EU water directive, which nudges national riverbed restoration efforts through a top-down process (such as in the Lithuanian case). In other cases, coupling between different policy areas and scales is taking place, such as in the latest education Law in Spain, where higher-level changes in education policy are creating synergies with municipal greening initiatives to offer a legal framework for embodied and nature-inclusive teaching and learning practices that can be applied in renaturalised schoolyards. If accompanied by shifting imaginaries, such as reframing renaturalised schoolyards' benefits through an emphasis on its relational value, or connecting nature initiatives holistically with other goals, such as health, an amplification beyond current rules, governance structures and values could be achieved. Ultimately, biodiversity innovations can only then unfold their full impact when they show that alternatives are possible and can be successful, for instance, when Foodpark Amsterdam has been successfully implementing a community land trust (Dutch Foodpark case), Sweden's forest owners shifted to continuous forest covers on a larger scale (Swedish case), schoolyard greening is fully embedded into the annual municipal budget (Spanish case), or syntropic farming has been established as the common agricultural production model (Portuguese case). It remains to be seen, however, if biodiversity innovations explored in BIOTraCes' case study will be successfully implemented over the long run and across various scales.

6 The complex interplay of bottom-up and top-down processes: enabler or disruptor of transformative change?

Transformative change can happen both through community action, that implements and experiments with diverse interventions and initiatives on the ground, but it can also be kickstarted through institutions and governance actors with ambitious future visions. Comparing the locally situated case study analyses, we can distinguish broadly four types of relations, processes, and dynamics unfolding between top-down and bottom-up approaches. These four types must be understood as prototypes with fuzzy boundaries, on which some of the cases map more neatly, and others are in-between different types. The prototypes are also to be understood in a temporal dynamic, as relationships and dynamics change over time. That is, close collaboration between top-down and bottom-up actors may have been absent in the past, but community- and trust-building efforts can lead to bringing different actor groups closer together, initiating a process of co-governance.

The first prototype concerns those cases where there are **either only top-down biodiversity initiatives present, or if bottom-up mobilization is happening, those processes are not coordinated**. This tends to result in policies and actions that are disconnected from the local context and realities, and that tend to overrun local knowledge. On the other side, local communities aim for a better integration with top-down processes, e.g., through sharing their knowledge and expertise, or by participating in decision-making processes. These dynamics can be observed, for example, in the Lithuanian case, where European legislation drives river renaturalization, yet local community action is, until now, lacking. The case study works here at the community level, aiming to initiate a process of awareness- and community building as a precursor for future bottom-up action. The Hungarian case also fits into this prototype, where there are top-down efforts to regulate nature conservation and agricultural and husbandry activities, that are however not interacting with local traditional knowledge holders, such as the herders at the heart of the Hungarian case. The case study shows how this marginalized group, through community-building efforts, is increasingly interested in sharing its expertise with policymakers.

The second prototype shows **institutional awareness for biodiversity challenges, also due to the existence of higher-level policies and frameworks**, such as the European Nature Restoration Law or the Water Framework Directive, that are supportive to local-level action as they draw attention to the importance for biodiversity innovations. Typical barriers encountered here, however, lie in the lack of hard criteria in the policies that lead to lacking or difficult implementation at lower policy scales. That is, the multi-level governance approach characterizing all case studies leads to institutional lock-ins. The Romanian case serves here as an example. This case is characterized by a higher-level legislation that aims for countering biodiversity loss, both at the national and European scale. However, those policies are often very disconnected from local realities and prioritize productivity of large-scale farmers over the maintenance of cultural landscapes. At the local level, there are increasing initiatives integrating local traditions and knowledge into the day-to-day economic activities, aiming to show that traditional ways-of-doing are not outdated, but innovative and able to bridge the human disconnect from local landscapes. The Swedish case also fits into this prototype, with national policies for forestry derived from long-term interactions of governance and the forestry impact sector. Like the Romanian case, those policies aim for a high-level of production, biodiversity here only

takes a subordinate role. At the local level, there are some private forest owners that try to implement small-scale actions more closely aligned with nature-inclusive ways of doing and thinking. The Dutch Foodpark case can further be considered an example of this prototype. Although the municipality is still promoting industrialization efforts at the cost of the biodiversity innovation, there are also ideas in place that aim for a better integration of the social and ecological aspects through top-down processes (e.g. the Doughnut economy), and to some small degree support the local innovation, as can be seen in Foodpark Amsterdam winning the municipal tender. However, despite the institutional awareness hard policy criteria are still missing that assure an actual implementation of those ideas.

The third prototype consists of a **closer collaboration between institutional and community actors**, e.g., through participatory processes or deeper levels of co-governance that include different local actor groups at different stages of the decision-making. The challenges faced by this prototype lies in a possible participation fatigue, as especially community actors participate in their free time, or the risk of a perceived cooptation of the biodiversity innovation – if initially driven through bottom-up processes and then institutionalized. The Portuguese, the Spanish, and the Dutch ecovillage case are exemplary for this prototype as they all draw, in varying degrees, on a collaboration of local communities and municipalities. In the Spanish case, this takes place through interactions between the municipality's different departments and the educational communities to renaturalizing schoolyards, in the Portuguese case, agricultural and community niche innovators draw on municipal support to amplify local innovations and on close collaboration with other civil society organizations to transform local food networks. The Dutch ecovillage case is characterized by different degrees of collaboration between community niche innovators and local and regional governments, that through smaller initiatives aim to drive change by challenging current lock-ins of the construction sector. While the ecovillage initiative still is not fully supported institutionally, smaller policy changes, however, indicate small shifts in the way of doing and thinking.

The last prototype describes those cases in which **institutional initiatives are either completely absent or present yet work against the biodiversity innovation**. In this prototype, bottom-up processes are continuously threatened by the status quo and current practices driving environmental degradation and biodiversity loss. An example for this prototype can be seen in the Italian case, where institutional and economic actors promote large scale photovoltaic plants and extractivist agricultural endangering the health of the local social-ecological systems. There are strong local movements, advocating for paradigm change, and implementing collective actions to overcome the productivist logics and lock-in imaginaries of the local landscapes as backwards. These niche innovators, however, refuse processes of institutionalization due to lacking support.

These four prototypes encountered in the BIOTraCes cases show the challenges that local biodiversity innovations face when aiming for transforming current governance forms through alternative, nature-inclusive practices, and based on new social-ecological imaginaries. They show the complexity and context-dependency of social-ecological constellations and processes that strongly influence the if and how of transforming social-ecological relations locally and across scales, as well as in the dominating values and worldviews.

Figure 2. BIOTraCes prototypes of top-down and bottom-up dynamics supporting or challenging transformative change.

Top-down & bottom-up approaches

7 Conclusion

Driving transformative change towards nature-positive and -inclusive futures is a complex process as change needs to occur at the practical, political and personal sphere. The analysis of the BIOTraCes case studies findings shows how those processes are highly complex and encounter many obstacles along the way. They also show that to be able to really transform social-ecological systems along many scales, close collaboration between many different actors is needed. This requires a better integration of the multiple efforts made through top-down and bottom-up processes and of the many knowledge and value systems that characterize the diversity of the social-ecological systems. Spaces for community and trust building are thereby quintessential, together with close collaboration of institutional actors and local communities and niche innovators. While the case studies point to the many shortcomings of the current ways of doing, structuring and thinking, they also give hope by visualizing the many positive examples that are already happening, where communities are coming together, dreaming and envisioning alternative futures. They show how community efforts already could achieve small changes in the system, either by disrupting, challenging or through close cross-sectoral collaboration.

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